

Organizational Justice's Impact on Counterproductive Work Behavior : A Moderated Effect of Emotional Intelligence (Study on Employees at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency)

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Abstract:- This study aims to examine the moderating role of emotional intelligence on the effect of organizational justice on counterproductive work behavior (CWB). This type of research is causal associative research with a quantitative approach. Sampling was taken using proportional random sampling technique, namely as many as 72 respondents were taken from a total population of 256 employees at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency. Data analysis used the PLS-SEM technique with Smart PLS 4 software. The results showed that organizational justice had a significant negative effect on CWB with a path coefficient value of -0.578 , a t statistic value of $5.973 > 1.96$, and a P value of $0.000 < 0.05$, and emotional intelligence could strengthen the influence of organizational justice on CWB with a path coefficient value of -0.234 , a t statistic value of $2.016 > 1.96$, and a P value of $0.044 < 0.05$.

Keywords:- Emotional Intelligence, Organizational Justice, Counterproductive Work Behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) are generally recognized as a major strategic issue and a source of competitive advantage for all organizations (Machado & Davim, 2018). Human resources are considered valuable because they have different skills (Marchington et al., 2021). Human resources have an important role both as planners, actors, and determinants in realizing organizational goals (Tanjung, 2020). So, to realize this requires quality human resources who can carry out their duties properly. However, on the contrary, this will not materialize and will even cause losses if the human resources do not carry out their duties properly and violate organizational norms by carrying out counterproductive work behavior.

Counterproductive work behavior (CWB) is a series of intentional actions in the workplace that intend to harm the organization and interested parties (coworkers, clients, customers and supervisors) (Rogelberg, 2007). Mehmood et al. (2022) explained that CWB can occur in public and

private organizations, and the consequences of such behavior are proven to be detrimental to employees, stakeholders, organizations, communities, and even countries. CWB can be measured by CWB Interpersonal (CWB-I) and Organizational CWB (CWB-O) indicators. CWB-I is interpersonally targeted deviant work behavior, such as bullying, endangering the welfare of organizational members or other stakeholders, meanwhile CWB-O is organizationally targeted deviant work behavior such as theft, production irregularities, absenteeism, or disloyalty (Mercado et al. al., 2018).

CWB can be caused by several factors. Sackett and DeVore (2001) categorize 6 factors that influence CWB, namely personality, job characteristics, work group characteristics, organizational culture, control system, and injustice. Meanwhile Rogelberg (2007) mentions two main factors that cause CWB, namely first individual factors including hostility, negative emotions, personality, impulsiveness, and drug addiction, second, situational antecedents which include job stressors, perceptions of fairness, experience, and group norms. Furthermore, in the research of Shao et al. (2022) explained three factors that cause CWB, namely organizational constraints, interpersonal conflict, and organizational injustice. Then the results of Nurmalaah et al. (2022) showed factors that can affect CWB, namely organizational justice, emotional intelligence, self-esteem, and work stress. From the factors mentioned above, the researcher wants to re-examine organizational justice and emotional intelligence factors.

Organizational justice is a perception felt by employees for the fair treatment they receive, whether in the form of attitude, treatment, or compensation (Jufrizen & Kandhita, 2021). The fairness of rules and processes, the distribution of organizational outcomes, and the treatment of employees by management and superiors are all factors that are taken into consideration by employees (Rogelberg, 2007). Organizational justice is one of the most studied predictors of counterproductivity (Mercado, et al., 2018). Akmal et al. (2020) revealed that employees with low perceptions of organizational justice would tend to take counterproductive actions compared to those with higher

perceptions of organizational justice. So that when the justice felt by employees is high, it will reduce counterproductive work behavior (CWB).

This relationship is proven by previous studies, for example, research conducted by Abbasi et al. (2022) , Nurmalaah et al. (2022) , Hany et al. (2020) Al-A'wasa (2018) shows a significant negative relationship between organizational justice and CWB. However, different results were found in the research by Rachmawati, et al. (2021) that all dimensions of organizational justice have no effect on CWB. Likewise, research conducted by Zakiy and Hariyanto (2022) found a difference, namely distributive justice did not affect CWB, but procedural justice and interactional justice had a negative and significant effect on CWB.

The results of previous research show that there is a research gap in the relationship between organizational justice and CWB. This shows that there are other variables that contribute to this relationship, one of which is the existence of emotional intelligence (EI). Emotional intelligence (EI) is the emotional ability to understand, manage, and use emotional information (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). Spector and Fox (2002) revealed that the perception of injustice will lead to negative emotions which in turn increase CWB. The presence of EI in an individual will be able to control these emotions and reduce CWB, so that EI can be a moderating variable.

The moderating role of emotional intelligence in the relationship between organizational justice and CWB is proven by previous research, namely research conducted by Badawy (2022) which explains that EI could moderate the relationship between perceived justice and counterproductive work behavior (CWB). However, the results are different from Devonish and Greenidge's (2010) study, which shows that emotional intelligence does not moderate the relationship between perceived fairness and CWB.

Based on the research gap stated above, the researcher is interested in conducting research related to the effect of organizational justice on counterproductive work behavior moderated by emotional intelligence in employees at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB)

Counterproductive work behavior (CWB) has been defined as intentional behavior that violates organizational norms and can harm the organization or its members (Hollinger, 1986 ; Robinson & Bennet, 1995; Spector & Fox, 2002 ; O'Boyle et al., 2011). Robinson and Bennett (1995) then presented a typology of CWB based on the level of severity and based on the target of the deviant behavior, whether the deviance was directed or targeted either at the organization (organizational deviance) or at members of the organization (interpersonal deviance).

Based on a study conducted by Bennett and Robinson (2000), CWB is categorized into 2 indicators, namely interpersonal deviation (CWB-I) and organizational deviation (CWB-O). CWB-I is an act that is done intentionally which then has the potential to harm individuals or members of the organization, such as making fun of, cursing, and acting harshly towards someone (Bennett & Robinson, 2000). Mercado et al. (2018) also describes CWB-I as interpersonally targeted deviant work behavior such as bullying, endangering the welfare of organizational members or other stakeholders. Other examples of CWB-I include hitting co-workers, insulting other people, and shouting at someone (Cohen, 2018). Meanwhile, CWB-O is an intentional act which then has the potential to harm the organization, such as dirtying the workplace, working slowly, and consuming alcohol at work (Bennett & Robinson, 2000). Mercado et al., (2018) explained that counterproductive work behavior targeted at the organization (CWB-O) includes behavior that directly harms the organization itself, such as theft, production irregularities, absenteeism, or disloyalty. Cohen (2018) also mentions that the behavior of damaging organizational property, deliberately doing the wrong job, and taking inappropriate work breaks are examples of CWB-O.

B. Organizational Justice (OJ)

Organizational justice (OJ) is an employee's assessment of fair and equal treatment in certain workplaces (Ghran et al., 2019; Mulang, 2022; Novitasari et al., 2020). According to Wiseman and Stillwell (2022) organizational justice is an individual's perception that events, actions, or decisions within an organization comply with fairness standards. Then Robbins and Judge (2022) explain organizational justice as the overall perception of employees about justice in the workplace which consists of the results obtained, the process for determining the results, and the quality of interpersonal treatment. Meanwhile Faeq and Ismael (2022) reveal that justice in an organization is seen as fundamental to social and psychological functioning, where the ability of individuals to predict the future treatment of an organization depends on their knowledge of the level of existing organizational justice.

The indicators used in this study are distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactional justice (Robbins & Judge, 2022). Distributive Justice is justice that is felt about the results obtained by employees (Robbins & Judge, 2022). An example of ditributive justice: an individual gets a raise they deserve (Robbins & Judge, 2022). Procedural justice is justice that is felt about the process by which results are determined (Robbins & Judge, 2022). This justice is felt when employees feel fair towards organizational procedures and regulations in making decisions or policies (Wirandika & Siswati, 2022). An example of procedural justice: an individual gets input about the process used to get a raise and there is a good explanation of why he or she received the raise (Robbins & Judge, 2022). Interactional justice refers to how a person gets equal treatment from a superior or co-worker or sensitivity to the quality of treatment between individuals (Robbins & Judge, 2022). There are 2 types of Interactional Justice. First, information

fairness, If managers explain major decisions to staff members and tell them of issues within the company, information fairness will be present. Managers who are detailed and honest with employees, employees will feel they are treated fairly. Second, interpersonal justice is related to respect and dignity for someone in treating others (Robbins & Judge, 2022). Respect is like doing small things, for example speaking politely with employees, regardless of the hierarchical position of employees in the organization (Akmal, et al., 2020). An example of interactional justice: the supervisor is very kind and praises the employee when he informs about the increase in salary (Robbins & Judge, 2022).

C. Emotional Intelligence (EI)

Salovey and Mayer (1990) view emotional intelligence (EI) as part of social intelligence which includes the ability to observe one's own and other people's feelings and emotions, to distinguish between them, and to use the information obtained to guide one's thoughts and actions. Robbins and Judge (2022) also revealed that emotional intelligence (EI) is a person's ability to: understand the emotions of oneself and others, understand the meaning of these emotions, and regulate one's own emotions in a certain way. Meanwhile, Rogelberg (2007) explains that emotional intelligence can be defined as a set of personality traits, competencies, or as intelligence.

Salovey and Mayer (1990) divided EI into four indicators, namely, self-emotional appraisal and expression, related to a person's ability to accurately understand their emotions and be able to express these emotions naturally. Appraisal and recognition of the emotions of others (others' emotional appraisal), this skill allows one to accurately measure affective responses in others and to select socially adaptive behaviors in response. Regulation of emotion in oneself relates to a person's skill to regulate his own emotions, so that it will allow a faster recovery from the onset of psychological stress. And finally, the use of emotion

to facilitate performance, it relates to individual skills in using their emotions properly to direct them to constructive activities and personal performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research used is causal associative with a quantitative approach. This research method relates to the collection and analysis of data that is structured and can be represented numerically. The main goal is to build accurate measurements (Goertzen, 2017). Data collection was carried out by survey method. This method is used because the selected sample is a portion of the existing population at the research site.

The total population is 256 employees at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency. Then, the number of samples taken by proportional random sampling technique is as many as 72 people. The sample consists of 47 civil servants and 25 non-civil servants. The data collection instrument used a questionnaire that refers to a likert scale with a score from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Questionnaire items consisted of 55 statements, consisting of statement items about CWB: 19 items (Bennett & Robinson, 2000), Organizational Justice: 20 items (Niehoff & Moorman, 1993), and Emotional Intelligence: 16 items (Wong & Law, 2002). Furthermore, the research data were analyzed using the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) with smart PLS 4.0.9 software.

IV. RESULTS

A. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

➤ Outer Loading

This outer loading is to describe how well the items reflect or describe variable measurements. The rule of thumb according to Chin, (1998), an outer loading value of more than 0.50 is acceptable (valid).

Fig 1 Path Diagram Model and Outer Loading Value

Based on Figure 1, all measurement items for each variable, both Organizational Justice, Emotional Intelligence, and Counterproductive Work Behavior, show an outer loading value of > 0.5, so it can be said that all indicators used are valid.

➤ *Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted*

Composite Reliability is to show how far the reliability of the variable is, while Average Variance Extracted shows how far the overall variable can explain the variation of the measurement items. The Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted values can be seen in the following table:

Table 1 Composite Reliability and AVE

Variable	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational Justice	0.961	0.553
Counterproductive Work Behavior	0.957	0.538
Emotional Intelligence	0.956	0.574

Based on Table 1, the Composite Reliability value of all research variables is more than 0.7, which indicates that the level of reliability is acceptable. While the AVE value of all research variables is more than 0.5, which means that convergent validity is accepted.

B. *Evaluation of the Structural Model (Inner Model)*

Structural model evaluation or hypothesis testing is carried out through the bootstrapping process. The test

results seen from the t-values for the two-tailed test is 1.96 (significant level = 5%). The results of testing the model hypothesis can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 Structural Model (Inner Model)

Relations between Variables	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values
Organizational Justice-CWB	-0.578	5.973	0.000
Emotional Intelligence x Organizational Justice-CWB	-0.234	2.016	0.044

From the table, it can be seen that all research hypotheses can be accepted, because the t statistic value is > 1.96 and the p value is <0.05 for each relationship between the variables (Yamin, 2022). First, the effect of organizational justice on CWB is negative and significant with a path coefficient value of -0.578, a t statistic value of 5.973 > 1.96, and a P value of 0.000 <0.05. Second, the role of emotional intelligence can strengthen the effect of organizational justice on CWB with a path coefficient value of -0.234, a t statistic value of 2.016 > 1.96, and a P value of 0.044 <0.05.

Furthermore, the moderating role of emotional intelligence on the effect of organizational justice on counterproductive work behavior can also be seen in the form of a simple slope analysis graph.

Fig 2 Graph of Simple Slope Analysis (Emotional Intelligence x Organizational Justice CWB)

The graph shows that there are 3 lines with relatively different slope levels. The red line shows a low level of individual EI, the blue line shows medium individual EI, and the green line shows high individual EI. The line shows that there is a CWB relationship that is getting lower when the organizational justice is getting higher, which can be seen in the decreasing level of the slope of the line. Then on the blue and green lines the slope is higher than the red line, which means that the CWB caused by organizational justice is lower in individuals with higher levels of emotional intelligence. So, it can be concluded that EI is able to strengthen the relationship between organizational justice and CWB, so that CWB will decrease.

C. Evaluation of Model Quality and Fit

This evaluation can be seen from several measures to declare the model acceptable, namely:

➤ *R Square*

R square value to describe the overall effect of exogenous / endogenous variables on other endogenes in a structural model. The R square value in this study is:

Table 3 R Square Value

Variable	R-Square
CWB	0.353

Table 3 shows that the influence of Organizational Justice on Counterproductive Work Behavior is 35.3%, which is included in the medium category (Chin, 1998) .

➤ *F Square*

The F square value is used to determine the influence of each exogenous variable on the endogenous variable. The F square value can be seen in Table 4 below.

Table 4 F Square Value

Variable	CWB
Organizational Justice	0.434
Emotional Intelligence x Organizational Justice	0.063

Table 4 shows that Organizational Justice has a high influence (F square = 0.434) on Counterproductive Work Behavior, while Emotional Intelligence x Organizational Justice has a moderate influence (F square = 0.063) on Counterproductive Work Behavior.

➤ *Q-Square*

Q Square is used to describe how well the model has predictive relevance. The Q Square value can be seen in Table 5. below:

Table 5 Q Square Value

Variable	Q Square
CWB	0.172

Table 5 shows a Q Square value of 0.172, which means that variables that affect CWB have low predictive relevance to CWB variables. Every change or variation of the CWB variable can be predicted by the Organizational Justice variable.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results showed that organizational justice had a significant negative effect on counterproductive work behavior. This means that the higher the perceived organizational justice in the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency, the lower the occurrence of counterproductive work behavior. Conversely, if the perceived lower organizational justice in the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency, the counterproductive work behavior that occurs will increase. This relationship is in accordance with social exchange theory (Blau, 1964), which shows that individuals develop exchange relationships based on their experiences with others (Cook et al., 2013). So that someone who gets good (fair) treatment will also show good behavior for his organization. In addition, the results of this study also support the theory of equity, which states that people compare rewards for their efforts with rewards received by others for their efforts (Sackett & DeVore, 2001). When someone feels that they are being treated unfairly, it will lead to CWB (Rogelberg, 2007), conversely, high perceived fairness will reduce employee involvement in CWB (De Clercq et al., 2021). The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Hany, et al. (2020), Abbasi, et al. (2021), and Nurmalaah, et al. (2022) which shows a significant negative relationship between organizational justice and CWB.

Additionally, this study's findings suggest that emotional intelligence can strengthen the impact of organizational justice on counterproductive work behavior at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency, where the effect is significantly negative. This means that emotional intelligence will strengthen the influence of organizational justice on counterproductive work behavior, so that counterproductive work behavior at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency will decrease. The results of this study are in accordance with the theory of fairness about CWB stating that employees who are not treated fairly tend to be involved in CWB (Rogelberg, 2007). This can be caused by the employee's emotional intelligence is low so that they are unable to control the emotions from perceived injustice thereby increasing CWB. On the other hand, employees with a high level of emotional intelligence are better to understand, regulate, and use their emotions well, so that in conditions of high perceived fairness, they can improve their performance and further reduce the occurrence of counterproductive work behavior. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Mahadiputra and Piartrini (2021), and Hendrayani and Dewi (2020), that EI strengthens the impact of organizational justice on CWB. Then research conducted by Badawy (2022) also shows that EI moderates the relationship between justice and CWB.

VI. CONCLUSION

➤ Based on the results of the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded from this study as follows:

- Organizational Justice has a significant negative effect on Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) in Bima Regency Regional Secretariat employees. This explains that the higher the perceived organizational justice at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency, the lower the occurrence of counterproductive work behavior. Conversely, if the lower the organizational justice at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency, the counterproductive work behavior that occurs will increase.
- Emotional Intelligence strengthens the influence of Organizational Justice with Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB) on Bima Regency Regional Secretariat employees. This means that employees with high emotional intelligence will strengthen the influence of organizational justice on counterproductive work behavior, so that counterproductive work behavior at the Regional Secretariat of Bima Regency will decrease.

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